

INFLUENCE OF STATOR BLADES AND EXHAUST HOOD ON FLUTTER PREDICTION IN THE LAST STAGE OF A LOW-PRESSURE STEAM TURBINE

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ABSTRACT

The last stage of low-pressure steam turbines is particularly susceptible to flutter, which can lead to structural damage. While aeroelastic modelling has advanced, the influence of upstream and downstream components, particularly the exhaust hood, remains underexplored.

This study examines the impact of exhaust hoods on the aerodynamic damping of last-stage blades. A simplified analytical model was first used to establish the methodology and clarify how to assess when non-uniform pressure distributions can contribute to aerodynamic work. The analysis considers both synchronous and non-synchronous vibration cases and shows that averaging aerodynamic damping coefficients over a single vibration period yields physically meaningful results.

The energy method was applied to obtain aerodynamic damping coefficients from numerical simulations across multiple computational domains, including configurations with and without stator blades, as well as with three alternative exhaust hood geometries. The results confirm that including both stator blades and the exhaust hood in the computational domain can modify aerodynamic damping. Moreover, they confirm the influence of exhaust hood geometries.

These results were compared with blade vibration measurements of a 380 MW steam turbine LP last stage in two working conditions, one of which resulted in flutter.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Exhaust Hood, Steam Turbine, Circumferential Distortion, Aerodynamic Damping

NOMENCLATURE

BTW backward traveling wave
CFD computational fluid dynamics
FTW forward traveling wave
FSI fluid–structure interaction
IBPA inter-blade phase angle
LP low-pressure
ND nodal diameter
QSE quasi-standard error

1 INTRODUCTION

The last stage of low-pressure (LP) steam turbines is susceptible to flutter, which can lead to structural damage. Although aeroelastic modelling has advanced significantly, the influence of upstream and downstream components, especially the exhaust hood, remains underexplored in flutter prediction. These components affect exit flow conditions, which may impact the aeroelastic stability of the rotor. However, to reduce computational cost, they are often simplified or omitted in many numerical studies.

Flutter in the last stage of LP turbines has been widely analysed in the literature. Masserey et al. [1] reported that cracks in the root region of last-stage rotor blades were caused by flutter.

Numerous other studies have also investigated steam turbine blade flutter. Rice et al. [2] presented results from a comprehensive validation program aimed at identifying safe operational limits with respect to flutter onset.

Efforts have been made to improve the precision of numerical modelling of blade flutter in the last stage of LP steam turbines. Petrie-Repar et al. [3] performed a detailed analysis of the final stage turbine row with long shrouded blades, includ-

ing the upstream stator row and the extended exhaust, to assess aeroelastic stability under realistic boundary conditions. Their work investigated the influence of gas models as well as reflective and non-reflective boundary conditions. Qi et al. [4] established an open 3D steam turbine flutter test case incorporating many key features relevant to flutter prediction, such as a long twisted blade, transonic flow at the rotor exit, mixing planes close to the blade, and a blade with low natural frequency. Zhuang et al. [5] validated the harmonic balance method for flutter prediction in the last stage of an LP steam turbine, also including the upstream stator and extended exhaust. Fuhrer and Vogt [6] investigated how different simulation approaches affect the computed aerodynamic damping of an LP steam turbine rotor.

The effect of stator blades on flutter has been highlighted by Huang et al. [7]. Their work demonstrated that including a stator row in flutter simulations can significantly alter the predicted aeroelastic behaviour of an LP turbine rotor compared to isolated blade-row models.

The impact of circumferentially non-uniform flow has been investigated more extensively in compressors than in steam turbines. Yan et al. [8], for instance, examined NASA Rotor 67 under distorted inlet conditions to assess how spatial flow non-uniformities influence classical flutter mechanisms. They also proposed a fast-calculation method for predicting aerodynamic damping coefficients at different nodal diameters under inlet distortion. Similarly, Herrick [9, 10] investigated fan flutter in the presence of inlet distortion, comparing clean inlet conditions with cases of total-pressure distortion at the aerodynamic interface plane. Wei et al. [11] studied blade flutter in a transonic compressor with sinusoidal inlet distortions of varying circumferential wave numbers as well as uniform inlet conditions. Their results showed that the impact of distortion is more pronounced in backward traveling-wave modes, whereas the effect on forward traveling-wave modes is relatively small. Nevertheless, the overall trends of aerodynamic damping characteristics remained essentially unchanged.

Chen et al. [12] analysed a transonic compressor rotor subject to inlet distortion at different rotational speeds. They demonstrated that the time-dependent fluctuations of aerodynamic damping are primarily caused by the mismatch between vibration and disturbance periods. At resonance conditions, however, the aerodynamic damping remains constant in time. For certain nodal-diameter traveling waves, identical damping values were obtained for all blades, while for others the blade-to-blade variations averaged out, resulting in negligible differences in mean aerodynamic damping between distorted and uniform inlet conditions.

The similar effects may arise in turbines, especially in the presence of exhaust hoods that introduce circumferentially non-uniform outlet conditions. The role of the exhaust hood itself has been discussed in the literature. Rzakowski et al. [13] performed a two-way fluid–structure interaction (FSI) analysis of

the last stage of a steam turbine with an exhaust hood. Based on their results, the authors concluded that including the exhaust hood in the simulation domain is important for obtaining aeroelastic predictions.

While previous studies have highlighted the importance of upstream stators and exhaust hoods for unsteady flow and aeroelastic behaviour, their impact on flutter prediction in the last stage of LP turbines, particularly in the context of classical flutter, and the effect of outlet geometry, including the exhaust hood, on the aeroelastic stability of last-stage steam turbine blades have not been satisfactorily studied.

In this paper, we investigate the influence of including the stator blades and the exhaust hood for predicting blade flutter in the last stage of a low-pressure steam turbine. Additionally, we explore whether modifications to the exhaust hood geometry can affect aerodynamic damping characteristics.

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL

Yan et al. [8] proposed a *Fast Calculation Method* for estimating the aerodynamic work on blades caused by non-uniform pressure distributions at the compressor inlet. Based on the results for all blades obtained for 0ND (zero nodal diameter), they can obtain the aerodynamic damping coefficient for other nodal diameters. Similar assumptions [8] can be applied to construct an analytical model that provides physical insight into the influence of exhaust hoods in turbines. In particular, this approach helps to clarify how results obtained with and without exhaust hoods can be compared to determine whether the exhaust hood affects aerodynamic damping and, consequently, rotor flutter stability. To illustrate this, we introduce a simplified model.

2.1 Influence of the non-uniform pressure distribution

Consider a radial section of the rotor blade row with tuned blades, where all the blades vibrate at the same angular frequency ω_B , with period T_B and amplitude δ_{\max} . The rotor rotates with angular velocity ω_R and revolution period T_R . Let ϕ denote the inter-blade phase angle (IBPA), and ψ_j the initial angular position of the j -th blade relative to the first blade, in a row with n_{bl} blades.

The aerodynamic work of the j -th blade over a time interval T is:

$$W_j = \int_0^T F_j \dot{x}_j dt, \quad (1)$$

where F_j is the force acting on the blade and $x_j = \delta_{\max} \sin(\omega_B t - j\phi)$ is its displacement.

The total force is decomposed into two components:

$$F_j = F_j^b + F_j^o. \quad (2)$$

where F_j^b represents the blade-to-blade interaction [14], and F_j^o arises from the circumferentially non-uniform pressure distribution. The latter can be written as:

$$F_j^o(t) = F_{\text{out}}(\psi_j + \omega_R t), \quad (3)$$

where F_{out} is a bounded, continuous, 2π -periodic (2π does not need to be a minimal period) function of zero mean. Expanding F_{out} as a uniformly convergent Fourier series gives:

$$F_{\text{out}}(\alpha) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [a_n \cos(n\alpha) + b_n \sin(n\alpha)]. \quad (4)$$

If a common period T exists such that $T = pT_B = qT_R$ ($p, q \in \mathbb{N}$), then unless $\omega_B = m\omega_R$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$ (synchronous condition), the work contribution from the non-uniform pressure (non-synchronous condition) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} W_j^o &= \int_0^T F_j^o \dot{x}_j dt = \\ &= \int_0^T F_{\text{out}}(\psi_j + \omega_R t) \delta_{\max} \omega_B \cos(\omega_B t - j\phi) dt \\ &= \delta_{\max} \omega_B \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[a_n \int_0^T \cos(\omega_R n t + n\psi_j) \cos(\omega_B t - j\phi) dt + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + b_n \int_0^T \sin(\omega_R n t + n\psi_j) \cos(\omega_B t - j\phi) dt \right] = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

This result indicates that, when integrated over the full common period of vibration and rotation, the non-uniform pressure distribution does not contribute to the aerodynamic work. Since no specific form of the pressure distribution is assumed, this conclusion holds for any distribution. In practice, however, the timescales associated with a full common period can be very long.

In the synchronous case, where $\omega_B = m\omega_R$ for some m , we define $h = \omega_B - m\omega_R$, the calculated the limit is:

$$\begin{aligned} W_j^o &= \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \int_0^T F_j^o \dot{x}_j dt = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \delta_{\max} \omega_B T [a_m \cos(m\psi_j + j\phi) + b_m \sin(m\psi_j + j\phi)]. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

This shows that in synchronous case the non-uniform pressure systematically contribute to the aerodynamic work, with the

same value repeating for the j -th blade in every common period. The contribution depends on the blade's initial angular position and its phase relative to the other blades. For specific nodal diameters, the values obtained from Eq. (6) can be constant for all blades. Chen et al. [12] reported such a case for 3ND BTW (three nodal diameter backward traveling waves) when considering the case when $\omega_B = 3\omega_R$, and Eq. (6) provides theoretical confirmation of this behaviour as $m\psi_j + j\phi = \text{const}$ for $m = 3$ and ϕ corresponding to 3ND BTW. Yan et al. [8] reported such a case for 2ND BTW when $\omega_B = 2\omega_R$.

If no common period exists, the integral can be interpreted as an almost-periodic function. In this case, averaging over an infinite period yields:

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T F_j^o(t) \dot{x}_j(t) dt = 0, \quad (7)$$

implying that the long-time contribution of the non-uniform pressure averages out.

Although this reasoning considered a single radial section, no assumption was made about which section was analysed. Therefore, the conclusions hold for the entire blade. The simplified analysis demonstrates that non-uniform outlet pressure does not contribute to aerodynamic work in non-synchronous cases when integrated over the full period. However, this does not imply that non-uniformity has no effect. It can still influence the blade-to-blade interaction force F_j^b in Eq. (2), and thus affect aerodynamic damping.

2.2 Averaging the aerodynamic damping coefficient

To assess whether a non-uniform pressure distribution influences the aerodynamic damping coefficient, it is necessary to evaluate the aerodynamic work over a common period of blade vibration and rotor revolution. However, such common periods can be extensive. Several authors [9, 10, 12] therefore proposed averaging the aerodynamic damping values over all blades in a row within a single vibration period. Convergence of such averages has been observed in practice.

Consider a single vibration period $T_B = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_B}$ of a rotor blade initially located at angular position ψ and with phase angle θ relative to the first blade. For the k -th vibration cycle, the aerodynamic work contribution from the non-uniform pressure is:

$$W_{\text{cycle}}^o = \int_{kT_B}^{(k+1)T_B} F_{\text{out}}(\psi + \omega_R t) \delta_{\max} \omega_B \cos(\omega_B t - \theta) dt \quad (8)$$

Since T_B is not, in general, a common period, this integral is not necessarily zero. In other words, aerodynamic damping values can differ when computed over a single vibration period.

Over the full common period, the non-synchronous contributions would cancel out.

Let us treat the result of Eq. (8) as a function $W_{cycle}^o(\psi, \theta)$ of the blade position and phase. Its average over $(\psi, \theta) \in [0, 2\pi]^2$ is:

$$\frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \iint_{[0, 2\pi]^2} \int_{kT_B}^{(k+1)T_B} F_{out}(t, \psi) \dot{x}(t, \theta) dt d\psi d\theta = 0, \quad (9)$$

provided that $\omega_B \neq n\omega_R$ for all integers n . Thus, in the non-synchronous case, averaging removes the influence of non-uniform pressure loads.

This explains why blade-to-blade averaging, as used by Herrick [9, 10] and others, can recover physically meaningful damping values. In effect, the averaging acts as a quasi-Monte Carlo approximation of the continuous integral. Blade phase angles and circumferential positions serve as the sampling sequence. The approximation error can then be bounded by inequalities such as the Koksma–Hlawka bound [15] and depends on the discrepancy of the sampling sequence.

The results from additional vibration cycles can also be included in the averaging, as each cycle provides sampling points of Eq. (8). When the nodal diameter is not relatively prime to the number of blades, the data provide new information for the approximation, provided that the total number of periods remains smaller than the least common multiple of the vibration and rotation periods.

Using this approach, the contribution of non-uniform pressure can be separated from the total aerodynamic work, thus enabling a comparison of the averaged components from blade-to-blade interactions. Any difference between averages calculated for models with and without an exhaust hood, or between models with different exhaust hood geometries, indicates that the exhaust hood influences flutter predictions by modifying blade-to-blade aerodynamic interactions.

Nevertheless, caution is required. Herrick [10] observed that averaged values suggested minimal stability in a one-way coupled simulation, whereas a two-way coupled approach predicted instability. This emphasizes the importance of estimating the approximation error when relying on averaging procedures.

2.3 Examples

To illustrate the model, two example cases are considered. The first is NASA Rotor 67, analysed by Yan et al. [8] (Example 1), and the second is an open 3D steam turbine flutter test case [4] (Example 2). The key parameters of these rotors are summarized in Tab. 1, and the assumed non-uniform outlet forces F_{out} are shown in Fig. 1.

Yan et al. [8] analyzed a synchronous case. In their study, the aerodynamic work was computed for one rotor revolution corresponding to two vibration periods. In this case, the aerodynamic

FIGURE 1: FORCES USED IN THE EXAMPLES.

work resulting from non-uniform pressure can be calculated using:

$$W^o = \int_0^T F_{out}(\psi + \omega_R t) \delta_{max} \omega_B \cos(\omega_B t - \theta) dt \quad (10)$$

where T is the common period of vibration and rotation, ψ the angular position of the blade and θ its phase relative to the first blade. By calculating Eq. 10 for every ψ and θ , and by normalizing the results to the maximum value, the aerodynamic work distribution shown in Fig. 2a is obtained. The black dots in Fig. 2a and 2b denote the ψ and θ points corresponding to the 22 blades in the rotor row for a given nodal diameter. In Fig. 2a, the black dots all correspond to the 2ND BTW mode. Here, all the blades have the same aerodynamic work value. However, this is not always the case. Fig. 2b shows the aerodynamic work distribution for the 2ND FTW (two nodal diameters forward traveling wave) and the blades have various aerodynamic work values. These findings are consistent with the numerical results reported by Yan et al. [8]. Moreover, the same distributions can be reproduced using Eq. (6), after normalization to the maximum value.

For Example 2 (Fig. 1 and Tab. 1), the aerodynamic work W_{cycle}^o , as defined in Eq. (8), resulting from non-uniform outlet pressure was calculated for a single blade vibration period. The parameters (Tab. 1) correspond to the open 3D steam turbine flutter test case [4] with a sinusoidal outlet force (Fig. 1). The resulting distributions of $W_{cycle}^o(\psi, \theta)$ are shown in Fig. 3 and in Fig. 4. Each figure illustrates the values of W_{cycle}^o for all ψ and θ angles. The black dots represent the W_{cycle}^o for 24ND

TABLE 1: ROTOR PARAMETERS FOR EXAMPLES.

Parameter	Example 1	Example 2
Rotor blade count	22	65
ω_R	16043 RPM	3000 RPM
ω_B	534 Hz	132.08 Hz

(a) 2ND BTW. (b) 2ND FTW.

FIGURE 2: AERODYNAMIC WORK IN A SYNCHRONOUS CASE.

FTW mode in Fig. 3 and for 3ND BTW mode in Fig. 4. Fig. 3a shows one period, Fig. 3b six periods, Fig. 4a one period, and Fig. 4b seven periods.

(a) ONE PERIOD. (b) SIX PERIODS.

FIGURE 3: $W_{cycle}^o(\psi, \theta)$ FOR 24ND FTW.

(a) ONE PERIOD. (b) SEVEN PERIODS.

FIGURE 4: $W_{cycle}^o(\psi, \theta)$ FOR 3ND BTW.

Fig. 3b and Fig. 4b show how sampling quality can be improved by combining data from multiple vibration periods. This approach provides a denser distribution, allowing for a more precise averaging of aerodynamic work. Nevertheless, care must be taken to ensure that sampling remains sufficiently uniform when additional periods are included.

The sampling of the $W_{cycle}^o(\psi, \theta)$ in Fig. 3a is satisfactorily uniform, whereas it is much less uniform in Fig. 4a.

3 METHODOLOGY

The first aim of this study is to determine the influence of the presence of stator blades and an exhaust hood on aerodynamic damping in the last-stage rotor of a turbine. Here, averages of aerodynamic damping values can be obtained and compared from models with and without these components. If the differences exceed the estimated averaging error, it would indicate that the presence of the components influences flutter stability. The second aim is to study the effect of exhaust hood geometry, and this can be achieved by applying various geometries. Only if the differences exceed the averaging error, the influence of the hood geometry can be confirmed.

The aerodynamic damping characteristics were obtained through flutter analysis. This was performed using the energy method [16] based on evaluating the aerodynamic damping of blade vibration for a range of IBPAs, which describe traveling-wave vibrations according to Lane's model [17]. In this model, all blades are assumed to vibrate with the same frequency and amplitude with a constant phase shift between adjacent blades (IBPA).

The analysis begins by computing the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the blades using finite element analysis with centrifugal pre-stress. For each mode, a small-amplitude vibration is imposed, with the blades oscillating according to the mode shape and assumed IBPA. The resulting unsteady aerodynamic loads are then calculated numerically using computational fluid dynamics (CFD), and the aerodynamic work over one vibration cycle is determined as:

$$W_{cycle} = \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} \int_{\Sigma_{blade}} p \vec{v} \cdot \hat{n} dA dt \quad (11)$$

where Σ_{blade} is the blade surface, T the vibration period, p the pressure on the blade surface, \vec{v} the vibration velocity, and \hat{n} the outward surface normal.

The IBPA is related to the nodal diameter (ND) of the vibration mode by:

$$IBPA = \frac{2\pi ND}{N_{bl}}$$

where N_{bl} is number of blades in the blade row and ND is the nodal diameter $0 \leq ND \leq \left\lfloor \frac{N_{bl}}{2} \right\rfloor$. In this study, $N_{bl} = 53$, so the number of possible nodal diameters is $ND = 0, 1, \dots, 26$.

The aeroelastic stability is then assessed by examining the aerodynamic damping, which is the normalized form of aerodynamic work. In this study, the following normalization is used:

$$\xi = -\frac{W_{cycle}}{mf^2 A_{norm}^2} \quad (12)$$

where ξ is the aerodynamic damping coefficient, m the blade mass, f the natural frequency of the blade and A_{norm} the maximum displacement of the blade. A positive damping indicates stable vibration, while a negative damping corresponds to energy transfer from the flow to the structure, which can lead to flutter.

3.1 Research Subject

The subject of this study is the rotor blade of the last stage of the LP section of a modernized 18K360 steam turbine. The rotor blade of the last stage of the LP section is shown in Fig. 5.

FIGURE 5: GEOMETRY OF TURBINE ROTOR BLADE.

3.2 Modal analysis

The first step of the energy method was a finite element analysis of the rotor blade shown in Fig. 5. This analysis aimed to determine the mode shapes and natural frequencies of the blade. The simulations were carried out in ANSYS Mechanical APDL [18]. Eight-node hexahedral elements were used for the discretization. The boundary condition was defined as a fixed support applied to the upper parts of the root teeth.

For the aeroelastic study, only the first vibration mode was considered. This was because flutter in last-stage steam turbine blades typically occurs at this frequency, and previous studies have shown that negative aerodynamic damping appears only for the first natural frequency (which was experimentally confirmed [1, 19, 20]).

3.3 CFD Analysis Setup

The second step of the energy method involved calculating the work-per-cycle of a blade, based on the loads acting on the blade during turbine operation with its motion obtained from modal analysis. These loads were determined numerically using CFD.

To investigate whether including the stator blades and the exhaust hood in the model affects the aerodynamic damping coefficient values, several computational domains were prepared:

1. Rotor (R) model including only the rotor blades (Fig. 6a).

2. Stator + Rotor (SR) model including all the stator and rotor blades (Fig. 6b).
3. Rotor + Exhaust Hood (RE) model included the rotor blades with an exhaust hood, but without the stator (Fig. 6c).
4. Stator + Rotor + Exhaust Hood (SRE) model including the stator, rotor blades and an exhaust hood modelled on a real exhaust hood (Fig. 6d).

Numerical simulations were performed for two turbine working conditions within a blade vibration risk zone, Fig. 7. These were obtained from blade vibration amplitude measurements of the last stage in a 380 MW steam turbine. In Fig. 7, working condition 1 results in flutter.

FIGURE 6: CFD COMPUTATIONAL DOMAINS.

Additionally, to examine the influence of exhaust hood and its induced pressure distribution on the aerodynamic damping characteristics, two alternative exhaust hood geometries were simulated in addition to the real one. In these models, the stator blade row was also included. The CFD model of the real exhaust hood is shown in Fig. 6d. The circumferential pressure distribution generated by this hood was expected to be close to sinusoidal. This configuration is referred to as **exhaust hood 1** (EH 1). The first alternative exhaust hood (CFD model in Fig. 8a)

FIGURE 7: WORKING CONDITIONS.

was expected to generate a pressure jump near the end of its spiral geometry. This configuration is referred to as **exhaust hood 2** (EH 2). The second alternative exhaust hood had steam outlets on two sides (CFD model in Fig. 8b) and was expected to generate a sinusoidal pressure distribution at twice the frequency of exhaust hood 1. This configuration is referred to as **exhaust hood 3** (EH 3).

FIGURE 8: CFD COMPUTATIONAL DOMAINS OF THE ALTERNATIVE EXHAUST HOODS.

The aerodynamic loads were determined by numerically solving three-dimensional, compressible Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations with an assumed blade motion. The commercial solver ANSYS CFX [18, 21] was used. The governing equations were closed using the Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model, which blends the $k-\omega$ formulation with the $k-\epsilon$ model. Near-wall turbulence was modelled with an adaptive approach that switches between a low-Reynolds-number resolution for the viscous sublayer and the logarithmic wall-function method, depending on the local dimensionless wall distance (y^+). Advection terms were discretized

using the High-Resolution scheme, which adaptively blends first-order upwind and second-order central differencing to maintain second-order accuracy while keeping the solution bounded. Diffusion terms followed the standard finite-element approach, where shape functions were used to evaluate spatial derivatives. Temporal discretization was performed with the second-order implicit backward Euler method, with each time-step iterated 10 times. Pressure–velocity coupling was modelled by the coupled algebraic multigrid solver of CFX.

At the inlet, distributions of total pressure, total temperature, and axial flow angle were imposed as boundary conditions. For models including the stator (Stator + Rotor and Stator + Rotor + Exhaust Hood, as well as those with exhaust hoods 2 and 3), these distributions were based on measurements from the real turbine. In models without the stator (Rotor and Rotor + Exhaust Hood), the inlet distributions were derived from stationary CFD simulations of the corresponding Stator + Rotor and Stator + Rotor + Exhaust Hood cases. In these simulations, the relative motion between rotating and stationary components was neglected using a Frozen Rotor interface. The turbulence intensity was set to 5% for all models. The inlet boundary was specified as reflective, since imposing a non-reflective condition consistently caused numerical overflow. This issue was particularly severe in models without a stator row, where the inlet flow to the rotor was supersonic. In such cases, CFX does not support a stable non-reflective boundary treatment.

At the outlet, a non-reflective static pressure boundary condition was applied for the Rotor and Stator + Rotor models, while an opening boundary condition with average static pressure was used for the others. All solid surfaces in the computational domain were assumed to be no-slip and adiabatic. General information about the model parameters is provided in Tab. 2. For quantities that vary between the two working conditions, the values are presented in a single cell as working condition 1 / working condition 2.

The physical timestep was 7.92×10^{-5} s, corresponding to approximately 253 timesteps per rotor revolution at 3000 RPM.

The assumed working fluid was an ideal gas. The steam in the considered stage was wet during measurements, so the ideal gas assumption does not reflect reality. However, the validation presented in Sec. 3.4 shows that the model reproduces the pressure distributions accurately.

The rotor blades vibrated with the assumed motion, and the mesh was updated using the displacement diffusion model, which solves diffusion-type equations to adjust the positions of unconstrained mesh nodes while preserving the relative distribution of the initial mesh. The maximum blade displacement, applied at the tip, was set to 1.5 mm.

A multi-block O-H-type structured grid was used for the blade computational domain, with O-blocks surrounding each blade and H-blocks filling the inter-blade passages. The exhaust hood domains were meshed with O-type grids for exhaust hoods

1 and 3, and a multi-block hex-dominant grid for exhaust hood 2. The selection of the mesh for the rotor blade passage was based on a grid-independence study. These simulations were steady-state and performed on a single blade passage. The resulting axial and circumferential force distributions along the blade span for the tested meshes are shown in Fig. 9. Thus a mesh with 180,000 elements per rotor blade passage was selected for the flutter analysis. In all considered models, the average y^+ value on the surface of the blade was lower than 7. In practice, the y^+ was higher than 1 only at the leading and trailing edges and at the blade tips.

FIGURE 9: FORCE COMPONENTS DISTRIBUTIONS ALONG THE BLADE SPAN FOR DIFFERENT GRIDS.

TABLE 2: SIMULATION MODEL PARAMETERS AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS.

Parameter	Value
Stator blade count	46
Rotor blade count	53
Rotation speed	3000 RPM
Average inlet total pressure	38800 Pa / 36200 Pa
Average inlet total temperature	348 K / 347 K
Outlet static pressure	10450 Pa / 15000 Pa
Specific heat	2080 $\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$
Maximum blade displacement	1.5 mm
Turbulence model	SST

3.4 Validation of numerical model

The CFD results were validated against empirical measurements obtained on the reference turbine [22]. The steam parameters were measured at the inlet to the last stage, downstream of the rotor, and in the condenser. Due to available instrumentation, the only direct possibility for CFD validation was through pressure measurements downstream of the rotor blade row. These measurements were performed using two probes located at circumferential positions of 10° and 78° from the vertical axis, in the direction of rotation.

A comparison between the reference turbine total pressure data and the results from the Stator + Rotor + Exhaust Hood model is shown in Fig. 10. The agreement between the CFD predictions and the measurements is good. The differences are probably due to geometric simplifications in the model.

FIGURE 10: TOTAL PRESSURE MEASURED AT TWO CIRCUMFERENTIAL POSITIONS.

The empirical study also included mass flow and temperature measurements. The measured mass flow rate was 105.6 kg/s, while the CFD model predicted 104.4 kg/s. The largest discrepancies occurred in the temperature distribution. The CFD predictions were significantly lower than the measured values. This difference is because the steam in the stage was wet, and the assumed ideal gas in the CFD model does not simulate this effect. Nevertheless, the pressure field was reproduced accurately.

The validation confirms that the adopted CFD model is capable of reproducing the pressure field with sufficient accuracy for aeroelastic analysis.

3.5 Convergence and Uncertainty of Blade-Averaged Aerodynamic Damping Coefficient

As explained in Sec. 2.2, the single-blade aerodynamic work values from the CFD for a single vibration period in the models with the exhaust hood do not generally converge. Previous studies [9, 10, 12] have shown that convergence can be achieved by

averaging the aerodynamic damping across all the blades on a disc.

From a mathematical perspective, this averaging is equivalent to approximating an integral using quasi-Monte Carlo methods. Estimating the error in such approximations is challenging. The Koksma-Hlawka inequality provides a theoretical bound, but its variation term is generally difficult to obtain. Methods based on Fourier and Walsh decompositions require additional assumptions about the underlying function [15]. In this study, where the aerodynamic damping values from CFD are essentially a black box, applying this bound is practically impossible. A quasi-standard error (QSE) can sometimes be used as a surrogate [23]. While QSE has been successfully used to construct confidence intervals, it has also been found to produce misleading results in some cases [24].

Two practical questions arise when using averaging. First, how many vibration periods should be included, and, second, how many replications are required if the QSE proposed by Warnock-Halton is applied?

To determine the sufficient number of vibration periods for averaging, a simplified analytical analysis similar to the second example from Sec. 2.3 was performed for the rotor in Tab. 2 and an assumed sinusoidal load induced by the exhaust hood. Uniform sampling of blade position angles relative to the pressure distribution and phase angles was achieved for different numbers of nodal diameters and vibration periods. For some nodal diameters, uniform coverage was obtained after at least 15 periods. However, for six periods, the mean values from the analytical model came down to zero in all cases except 1 ND FTW and 1 ND BTW. Based on this, six periods were adopted in the present study as sufficient to suppress the influence of non-uniform pressure, consistent with the reasoning in Sec. 2.2.

The convergence of the averaged aerodynamic damping was then assessed by monitoring its evolution over successive periods. Convergence was assumed to be achieved when, in the last 6 periods, the standard error of the 6 mean values (corresponding to QSE with 6 replications) was below 0.0005. Cases that did not meet this criterion were excluded from further analysis.

For the convergent cases, the final value of the aerodynamic damping coefficient was taken as the average of all blade values from the last six periods, and the associated error was estimated as the standard error of these values. This procedure is not mathematically rigorous. Aerodynamic damping values correspond to deterministic sampling points (blade positions and phase angles) rather than random samples. Nevertheless, it is conservative. Comparative analyses of QSE with different numbers of replications consistently yielded lower error estimates than the standard error adopted here.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the numerical results for aerodynamic damping in a steam turbine LP last stage.

Models with a uniform outlet pressure distribution (Rotor and Stator + Rotor) showed relatively small discrepancies in the blade-to-blade aerodynamic damping coefficients. In contrast, inclusion of the exhaust hood produced large variations, where at the same IBPA, aerodynamic damping was positive in some blades and negative in others. Fig. 11, compares results for individual blades in one vibration cycle of the Stator + Rotor + Exhaust Hood model (SRE) with those of the Stator + Rotor model (SR). The larger connected symbols denote mean values. These variations are consistent with previous studies [9, 10, 12], reporting significant compressor blade-to-blade aerodynamic damping differences with non-uniform inlet pressure distributions, and with the analysis of Eq. (8) (Sec 2.2).

FIGURE 11: AERODYNAMIC DAMPING COEFFICIENTS FOR INDIVIDUAL SRE AND SR BLADES IN A SINGLE VIBRATION PERIOD.

4.1 Influence of including a stator and exhaust hood on aerodynamic damping

The results for the R, SR, RE, and SRE configurations (Sec. 3.3) are presented for working condition 1 (Fig. 7) Fig. 12, and for working condition 2 (Fig. 7) Fig. 13. The x -axis is the nodal diameter, and the y -axis is the aerodynamic damping coefficient (Eq. (12)). The values were averaged using the method described in Sec. 3.5.

Flutter occurred from IBPA -77° to -50° in the rotor model (R), from -115° to -35° in the stator and rotor model (SR), -89° to -51° in the rotor and exhaust hood model (RE), and -148° to -33° in the stator, rotor, and exhaust hood model (SRE). Here, the large IBPA range for flutter occurs when the stator and exhaust hood are included. High blade amplitude was measured in

FIGURE 12: AERODYNAMIC DAMPING COEFFICIENT - WORKING CONDITIONS 1.

FIGURE 13: AERODYNAMIC DAMPING COEFFICIENT - WORKING CONDITIONS 2.

working condition 1 (Fig. 7), though without the IBPA. Therefore, the numerical analysis agrees with the measurements.

A comparison between R vs SR (Fig. 12) for the aerodynamic damping coefficient in working condition 1 (Fig. 7) shows that the differences exceed the calculated error for all nodal diameters. The most considerable differences were for negative IBPAs. For RE vs SRE (Fig. 12), the difference exceeds the calculated error at 19ND BTW. This shows that the inclusion of the stator blade affected aerodynamic damping values.

The R and RE results might have been affected by the placement of the inlet boundary. Imposing total pressure, tempera-

ture, and flow direction directly at the rotor inlet could restrict the proper development of the upstream pressure field. Additionally, the reflecting inlet boundary condition may have introduced errors. A more definitive assessment would require non-reflecting inlet conditions. Despite these limitations, the results confirm Huang et al. [7], who shows that the inclusion of stator blades influences aerodynamic damping in steam turbines.

A comparison of R vs RE (Fig. 12) for condition 1 (Fig. 7) shows that the difference exceeds the calculated error at 6ND FTW. For SR vs SRE (Fig. 12), the differences exceed the calculated errors at 26ND BTW, 19ND BTW, 13ND FTW, and 26ND FTW. This means that the inclusion of the exhaust hood altered aerodynamic damping values.

For working condition 2 (Fig. 13), flutter occurred from IBPA -110° to -79° in the rotor model (R), from -99° to -66° in the stator and rotor model (SR), -90° to -88° in the rotor and exhaust hood model (RE), and -89° to -88° in the stator, rotor, and exhaust hood model (SRE). Here, the inclusion of the stator and exhaust hood with mechanical damping does not result in flutter, which is in agreement with the experimental results.

A comparison of R vs SR (Fig. 13) for condition 2 (Fig. 7) shows that the difference exceeds the calculated error for all nodal diameters. The differences were bigger for positive IBPAs. For RE vs SRE (Fig. 13), differences are within the error bars at all nodal diameters. Similarly, the stator could influence the results.

A comparison of R vs RE (Fig. 13) for working condition 2 (Fig. 7) shows that the differences exceed errors at 4ND FTW, 6ND FTW, 13 ND FTW, and 19ND FTW. For SR vs SRE (Fig. 13), the differences exceed errors at 6ND FTW. This means that the inclusion of the exhaust hood changed aerodynamic damping values.

4.2 Influence of the exhaust hood geometry on aerodynamic damping

Additional simulations were performed with two alternative exhaust hood geometries. A comparison was made between a 380 MW steam turbine exhaust hood (EH 1) and two theoretical exhaust hoods, a spiral exhaust hood (EH 2), and one with two outlets (EH 3). Each geometry was designed to produce a different circumferential pressure distribution, while maintaining similar flow parameters. These simulations were conducted only for working condition 1.

The radially averaged circumferential pressure distributions at the turbine outlet are presented in Fig. 14. Here, 0° corresponds to the vertical top radius, and the angle increases counterwise to the turbine rotation. The corresponding flow parameters for the three exhaust hoods are summarized in Tab. 3, where \dot{m} denotes the mass flow rate, P_{out} the average static pressure downstream of the rotor blade row, and τ_a the axial component of turbine torque.

FIGURE 14: AVERAGE PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION FOR THREE EXHAUST HOODS.

The mass flow rates were nearly identical in all three cases. In EH 1 and EH 3, the average pressure behind the rotor was slightly below the condenser pressure imposed at the outlet boundary, which can be attributed to minor stagnation in the diffuser region. By contrast, EH 2 produced a noticeably higher outlet pressure and a lower overall load. Despite these differences, the models remain suitable for comparing aerodynamic damping characteristics.

The resulting aerodynamic damping coefficients are shown in Fig. 15. For the three alternative exhaust hoods, flutter occurred from IBPA -148° to -33° in (EH 1), from -152° to -49° in (EH 2), and from -112° to -66° in (EH 3). This shows that exhaust hood geometries do influence the flutter region.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the effect of various rotor, stator, and exhaust hood configurations on aerodynamic damping in the last LP stage of a 380 MW steam turbine. The aerodynamic damping coefficients were obtained for the various configurations and working conditions.

1. A simplified blade row model was proposed for the first time to calculate the aerodynamic damping work with non-uniform pressure behind the blades. This explained why

TABLE 3: COMPARISON OF FLOW PARAMETERS FOR THREE DIFFERENT EXHAUST HOODS.

	EH 1	EH 2	EH 3
\dot{m} $\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{s}}\right]$	104.4	104.3	104.5
P_{out} [Pa]	10250	12158	10070
τ_a [N·m]	46487	40629	46881

FIGURE 15: AERODYNAMIC DAMPING COEFFICIENT FOR EXHAUST HOODS.

blade aerodynamic work averaging can produce meaningful results.

2. CFD simulations showed that including the stator blades in computer models can alter the aerodynamic damping. This effect was observed in models with stator blades, with and without the exhaust hood. However, these results may have been affected by the reflecting inlet boundary condition. Further studies with non-reflecting inlet boundaries are necessary.
3. The inclusion of the exhaust hood in the models influences aerodynamic damping. The effect can vary for different nodal diameters and working conditions.
4. The numerical results were compared with experimental measurements.
5. The influence of exhaust hood geometry on aerodynamic damping was determined. Additional studies are required to clarify this effect.

Overall, this study confirms that including the exhaust hood in the model can affect aerodynamic damping characteristics. More specifically, the results highlight that interactions between flow distortions induced by the exhaust hood and blade vibrations can influence flutter stability.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Masserey, Pierre-Alain, M. I., and Lorini, H., 2012. “Analysis and improvement of vibrational behaviour on the ND37 A last stage blade”. *VGB PowerTech*, **92**.
- [2] Rice, T., Bell, D., and Singh, G., 2007. “Identification of the Stability Margin Between Safe Operation and the Onset of Blade Flutter”. In *ASME Turbo Expo 2007: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, Vol. 5: Turbo Expo 2007 of *Turbo Expo*, pp. 637–648.
- [3] Petrie-Repar, P., Makhnov, V., Shabrov, N., Smirnov, E., Galaev, S., and Eliseev, K., 2014. “Advanced Flutter Analysis of a Long Shrouded Steam Turbine Blade”. In *ASME Turbo Expo 2014: Turbine Technical Conference and Exposition*, Vol. 7B: Structures and Dynamics, American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
- [4] Qi, D., Petrie-Repar, P., Gezork, T., and Sun, T., 2017. “Establishment of an open 3D steam turbine flutter test case”. In *12th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid dynamics & Thermodynamics*.
- [5] Zhuang, Q., Suzuki, R., and Munktel, E., 2023. “Aerodynamic and aeroelastic computations of a last stage steam turbine using harmonic balance methods”. In *15th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid Dynamics and Thermodynamics, ETC15, European Turbomachinery Society*.
- [6] Fuhrer, C., and Vogt, D. M., 2017. “On the Impact of Simulation Approaches on the Predicted Aerodynamic Damping of a Low Pressure Steam Turbine Rotor”. In *On the Impact of Simulation Approaches on the Predicted Aerodynamic Damping of a Low Pressure Steam Turbine Rotor*, Vol. 8: Microturbines, Turbochargers and Small Turbomachines; Steam Turbines of *Turbo Expo*.
- [7] Huang, X. Q., He, L., and Bell, D. L., 2006. “Influence of upstream stator on rotor flutter stability in a low pressure steam turbine stage”. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy*, **220**(1), pp. 25–35.
- [8] Yan, Z., Pan, T., Su, G., Li, Q., and Kielb, R. E., 2024. “Numerical Investigation of Classic Flutter Mechanism Under Circumferentially Non-Uniform Inlet Condition”. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, **146**(6).
- [9] Herrick, G., 2010. “Effects of Inlet Distortion on Aeromechanical Stability of a Forward-Swept High-Speed Fan”. In *46th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference & Exhibit*, Vol. 3.
- [10] Herrick, G., 2014. “Assessing Fan Flutter Stability in Presence of Inlet Distortion Using One-way and Two-way Coupled Methods”. In *50th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference*.
- [11] Wei, J., Chi, Z., Wang, S., Zheng, Q., Yan, W., and Jiang, B., 2025. “Probability evaluation of blade flutter in a transonic compressor with inlet distortion using SSA-DBEN model”. *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, **135**.
- [12] Chen, H., Xia, K., Deng, H., Zhu, M., and Teng, J., 2025. “Investigation of aeroelastic instability in a transonic compressor with low engine order distortion”. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, **159**.
- [13] Rzakowski, R., Gnesin, V., and Kolodyazhnaya, L., 2018. “Aeroelasticity Analysis of Unsteady Rotor Blade Forces and Displacements in LP Last Stage Steam Turbine with Various Pressure Distributions the Stage Exit”. *Journal of Vibration Engineering & Technologies*, **6**, p. 333–337.
- [14] Verdon, J. M., 1987. “Linearized Unsteady Aerodynamic Theory”. In *AGARD Manual on Aeroelasticity in Axial-flow Turbomachines: Unsteady Turbomachinery Aerodynamics*, M. F. Platzer and F. O. Carta, eds., Vol. 1 of *AGARD Manual on Aeroelasticity in Axial-flow Turbomachines*. AGARD, Neuilly-sur-Seine, ch. 2.
- [15] Lemieux, C., 2009. *Monte Carlo and quasi-Monte Carlo sampling*. Springer Series in Statistics Ser. Springer, New York.
- [16] Carta, F. O., 1967. “Coupled Blade-Disk-Shroud Flutter Instabilities in Turbojet Engine Rotors”. *Journal of Engineering for Power*, **89**(3), pp. 419–426.
- [17] Lane, F., 1956. “System Mode Shapes in the Flutter of Compressor Blade Rows”. *Journal of the Aeronautical Sciences*, **23**(1), pp. 54–66.
- [18] ANSYS, Inc., 2023. *Ansys Academic Research Mechanical*, Release 23.2.
- [19] Rzakowski, R., Kubitz, L., Gnesin, V., and Kolodyazhnaya, L., 2018. “Flutter of long blades in a steam turbine”. *Journal of Vibration Engineering & Technologies*, **6**, p. 289–296.
- [20] Rzakowski, R., and Szczepanik, R., eds., 2017. *Dynamics of last stage low pressure steam turbine rotor blades*. Wydawnictwo Instytutu Technicznego Wojsk Lotniczych.
- [21] ANSYS, INC., 2023. *Ansys Academic Research Mechanical, CFX-Solver Theory Guide*. Release 23.2.
- [22] Gardzilewicz, A., 2017. “Evaluating the efficiency of low pressure part of steam turbines based on probing measurements”. *Transactions of the Institute of Fluid-Flow Machinery*, **135**, pp. 41–56.
- [23] Halton, J. H., 2005. “Quasi-Probability: Why quasi-Monte-Carlo methods are statistically valid and how their errors can be estimated statistically”. *Monte Carlo Methods and Applications*, **11**(3).
- [24] Owen, A. B., 2006. “On the Warnock-Halton quasi-standard error”. *Monte Carlo Methods and Applications*, **12**(1).